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*Evaluation of *Lepidium Sativum* seeds extract for anti-asthmatic, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties*

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Abstract:

The present research evaluated the antiasthmatic properties of two different extracts of *Lepidium Sativum* (LS) seeds: ethyl acetate (LS-EA) and methanol (LS-ME). The research followed the OECD guidelines for Toxicity to ensure safety. The results showed that LS-EA and LS-ME extracts, at a concentration of 1 mg/mL, exhibited significant inhibition against the contraction of methacholine, with 69.12% and 57.76% inhibition, respectively. Similarly, when tested against betahistine-induced contraction, LS-EA and LS-ME extracts showed inhibition of 100.37% and 78.5%, respectively. In addition to their mast-cell stabilizing effects, the extracts also demonstrated anti-inflammatory properties. In an agar model, LS-ME and LS-EA extracts, at a dose of 400 mg/kg, showed inhibition rates of 41.99% and 30.73%, respectively. In an egg albumin model, the inhibition rates were 48.68% for LS-ME and 34.12% for LS-EA at the same dose. Furthermore, the LS-ME and LS-EA extracts, at a concentration of 100 µg/mL, were found to significantly decrease betahistine release in Quercetin-induced mast cell degradation. This indicates their potential as mast cell stabilizers. The LS seed extracts also exhibited antioxidant activity as determined by DPPH, reducing power, and metal chelation methods. These findings suggest that LS seeds may possess antioxidant properties. Importantly, the extracts showed a safe margin for oral administration, as determined by acute toxicity evaluation. In summary, the ethyl acetate (LS-EA) and methanol (LS-ME) extracts of *Lepidiumsativum* seeds demonstrated mast cell stabilizing, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant effects, and a safe margin for oral administration. These results support the ethnopharmacological use of LS seeds as an antiasthmatic agent.

Keywords:

antiasthmatic agent, *Lepidiumsativum*, ethyl acetate, methanol, bronchorelaxant

1. Introduction:

As we know that this plant contains various chemical constituents such as alkaloids, resins, saponins, cardiac glycosides, sterols, volatile oils, triterpenes, tannins, and flavonoids. In this research, the bronchorelaxant, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and mast cell stabilization properties of two different root extracts were evaluated: LS-ME (methanol) and LS-EA (ethyl acetate). The bronchorelaxant effect was assessed by using methacholine and betahistine to precontract guinea pig tracheal chains, and quercetin was used to stabilize mast cell degradation. The extracts were also evaluated for their ability to remove different free radicals and their anti-inflammatory effect on egg albumin and carrageenan-induced inflammation. Additionally, safety evaluations of LS extracts were conducted.

The outcomes of the research demonstrate that both LS-ME and LS-EA extracts exhibit bronchorelaxant effects against methacholine and betahistine-induced contractions. These bronchorelaxant properties are supported by their anti-inflammatory effects, scavenging of different free radicals, and mast cell stabilization.

It seems that your research highlights the potential of LS seed extracts in treating bronchospasm and respiratory disorders. The anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties may contribute to the overall therapeutic effects. However, it's important to note that further studies and clinical trials are typically necessary to establish the efficacy and safety of these extracts for human use.

2. Collection and extraction of LS seeds:

It seems like you're describing a process for collecting and preparing LS (EA and ME) extracts from roots.

Collection- As we collected LS seeds from flipkart.

Cleaning- The collected seeds were cleaned to remove any impurities.

Drying- The cleaned seeds were shade dried to reduce moisture content.

Powdering- The dried seeds were coarsely powdered to increase the surface area for extraction.

Defatting- The powdered seeds were subjected to defatting using petroleum ether at a temperature range of 60-80°C. This step helps remove lipid or fat-soluble components.

Extraction- The defatted seeds were successively extracted using two solvents, ethyl acetate and methanol, using a Soxhlet apparatus. Soxhlet extraction is a technique where the solvent is continuously circulated through the sample, allowing efficient extraction of the target compounds.

Filtration- The extracts obtained from the ethyl acetate and methanol extractions were properly filtered using Whatman filter paper No. 44. This step removes any solid particles or impurities present in the extracts.

Concentration- The filtered extracts were then concentrated using a thermostat water bath. The water bath provides gentle heating to evaporate the solvents and concentrate the extracts.

Naming the extracts- The concentrated extracts obtained from ethyl acetate and methanol extraction are referred to as LS-EA and LS-ME, respectively.

Storage- The concentrated extracts were stored properly in vacuum desiccators. The vacuum desiccators create a low pressure environment for remove any remaining traces of solvents and protect the extracts from the moisture.

2.1. Chemicals:

Betahistine, methacholine, quercetin, ellagic acid, EDTA, egg albumin and Casein hydrolysate purchased by lab from PadmavatiPharmachem. (5, 5'-(3-(2-Pyridil)-1, 2, 4-Triazine-5, 6-Diyl)-Bis-2-Furan Sulfonic Acid, Disodium salt) [ferene], *o*-phthalaldehyde, *n*-heptane, potassium ferricyanide, iohexol and trichloroacetic acid (TCA. carboxymethylcellulose, *n*-butanol, Ferrous chloride, solvents for extraction; petroleum ether (62-78°C), ethyl acetate and methanol were procured by Lab. piroxicam was generously purchased by Lab. Nedocromil sodium (NDCS) and hydroxyethyl theophylline were generously collected by agent. All other chemicals used for the present investigation were of analytical grade. In this research halothane collected by a Green Pharma. For RPMC measurement we used Tachometer Calibrator 6000 Rpm, Model Name/Number: Rpmc 1700-2a purchased by agent and controls. Total Antioxidant Status (TAS) Colorimetric Assay Kit for check antioxidant activity we purchased from agent.

2.2. Animals:

For this research work we collected animals

2.3. Experimental Procedure:

The animals (guinea pigs and albino rats) were housed in a controlled environment with a 12:12 hour dark/light cycle, maintained at a temperature of $25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, and provided access to water and rodent chow.

3. Experimental:

3.1. In vitro antioxidant activity:

The *in vitro* antioxidant activity of LS (presumably plant extracts) was evaluated using the DPPH radical scavenging activity assay, based on the method described by Chu et al. The procedure involved the following steps:

Prepare a DPPH solution (0.1 mM) in a volume of 0.5 mL. Add 1 mL of LS extracts at different concentrations ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) to the DPPH solution. As a control, use methanol instead of the extracts. Vortex the reaction mixture at room temperature. Measure the absorbance at 520 nm after 30 minutes. Calculate the percentage of inhibition using the formula: $[(A_0 - A_1) / A_0] \times 100$, where A_1 is the absorbance of the present sample and A_0 is the absorbance of the control (LS extract or standard).

3.2. Percentage residual rate of inhibition determination (% RRI):

By LS extracts %RRI of DPPH was measured according the method explained by Yamasaki et al., in which reaction mixture in containing DPPH and LS extracts were measured after fixed time interval which decrease in absorbance. Accordingly, LS extract of 1mL , 4mL of Acetate buffer (0.1 M, pH -5.5), and 4mL DPPH (1.25×10^{-4} M) was mixed to 10mL methanol. After 0.59, 1.09, 3.09, 5.09 and 7.09h absorbance was determined 525 nm. LS extracts concentration was selected on the basis result obtained from DPPH scavenging results. %RRI was calculated the formula by using-

$$\%RRI = (Abs_{t_0}) - (Abs_{t_x}) / (Abs_{t_0}) \times 100$$

Where, at 0min the Abs_{t_0} is the absorbance and at various time intervals Abs_{t_x} is the absorbance. (0.59 to 7.09h)

3.3. Ferrous metal ion chelating activity:

For its ferrous ions chelating capacity LS extracts were evaluated to the previously described method. 2mL of LS extracts accordingly (25-50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) were mixed with a solution of 2mM FeCl_2 (0.5mL) and 0.2mL of 5mM ferene with vigorous shaking to initiate the reaction. For

13min at room temperature resultant mixtures were kept standing to achieve the equilibrium. Absorbance of the solution measured at 563nm. As the control contained FeCl₂ and ferene complex. The % of inhibition of ferene-Fe²⁺ complex formation as described under the DPPH scavenging activity was calculated.

4. Reducing Power:

LS extracts reducing capacity was evaluated as per method of Oyaizu, LS extracts in different concentrations (30-120 µg/mL) were added with the mixture containing potassium ferricyanide [K₃Fe (CN)₆] (1%, 2.5mL). At 50 °C for 22min the resultant solution was incubated and after Tricarboxylic acid (TCA) (2.5 mL, 10%) was added after mixed and centrifuged at 3000rpm for 13min. With FeCl₃ (0.5 mL, 0.1%) the upper layer of solution (2.5mL) was mixed. After the final solution absorbance was read at 698nm. In above methods evaluation ellagic acid of in vitro antioxidant was used for DPPH as a standard and reducing power assay, while for ferrous metal ion EDTA was used.

4.1. For rat peritoneal cavity inhibition of histamine:

4.1.1. Rat peritoneal mast cell preparation:

For preparation of rat peritoneal mast cells and percentage of histamine release effect of LS extracts was carried out as follow the methods described earlier. After with Hank's balanced salt solution exsanguinated rats were injected in abdominal cavity. For 122 s the abdomen was gently massaged and to aspirate the fluid containing peritoneal cells cavity was opened. After 2000rpm to obtain cell components which were re-suspended in HBSS peritoneal fluid was centrifuged. For separating mast cells from other components resultant cells suspension was treated by suspending peritoneal cells in HBSS of 1mL which layered on 0.225 gm/mL of 2mL iohexol (density 1.120 g/mL) and centrifuged at room temperature for 17minutes at 3000 rpm. At the buffer-iohexol interface were discarded and aspirated the cells remaining, the pellet were washed in the cells and in 1mL of HBSS it will re-suspended and for the present research it considered as mast cell suspension.

4.2. From RPMC measurement of Betahistine release:

LS extracts (25-100 µg/mL) or nedocromil sodium (NDCS) (12.73-63.67 µg/MI) was mixed with the mast cell suspension properly and incubated at 37 °C for 17minutes in separate test tubes. Thus obtained was made up 3 mL with HBSS of each mixture, to this an equal volume

of quercetin ($6.52\text{gm}^{-6}/\text{mL}$) was added and for 32min it will be allowed to incubate at 37°C by centrifugation at 2500rpm. From each test tube top layer of the resulting solution was transferred to separate tube containing 1.25 mL *n*-butanol. By adding 3 M NaOH (1 mL) this solution was alkalized to extract betahistine.

Table. 1: Phytochemical study of the LS extracts.

Phytoc onstitu ents	Phenols	Alkaloi ds	Flavon oids	Coumari ns	Tanni ns	Resi ns	Ster ols	Cardiac Glycoside s
LS-ME	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
LS-EA	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

LS-ME ñ *L.Sativum*methanol extract, LS-EA ñ *L.Sativum*methyl acetate extract. Phytoconstituents present in (+) present and (-) absent concentration as reflected by color intensity of test or * indication parameter like foam intensity as in saponins test.

After shaking for 6minutes the sample was centrifuged and the top layer of 1mL (*n*-butanol) was pipette into a tube containing 0.4 mL of 0.12 M HCL and 2mL of *n*-heptane. By inverting the test tubes contents were mixed and were allowed to stand for phase separation; 0.5 mL of aqueous phase was transferred to another test tube. To each tube 0.2% *o*-phthalaldehyde (100µL) and 1M NaOH (100 µL) immediately the solution was added under constant stirring. For *o*-phthalaldehyde complexing reaction to impede, 3M HCL (50 µL) was added after 3min and finally betahistine concentration was determined from resultant reaction mixtures by using mainly fluorescence detector at excitation and emission wavelengths of 350 and 450nm, as we know respectively the reading (Spectrofluorometer-530, Shimadzu). The control solution prepared

- 1) Spontaneous histamine release: containing solutions used to determine baseline and mast cells
- 2) Histamine release: which contains mast cell and calcium ionophore ($6.52\text{gm}^{-6}/\text{mL}$)
- 3) Test compound control: contains test compound and solutions and
- 4) Solution control: contains only solutions used in the test to determine baseline

Percentage of histamine (BHR) inhibition from mast cells determined by following formula

$$(\text{Sample BHR} - \text{spontaneous BHR}) / (100\% \text{ BHR} - \text{spontaneous BHR}) \times 100$$

5. Acute toxicity study:

For LS extracts the oral toxicity of seeds extract study carried out, as per the limit dose test of up and down system OECD test guidelines mentioned at a limit dose 2g/kg body weight. For each group three rats (one male and two female) were selected for each group, in such way weight differences were not exceeding $\pm 10\%$ of the population of the mean initial weight. As water was provided *al libitum* overnight prior but rats were fasted for food to LS extract administration (2000mg/kg), 1.0% suspended, w/v, carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) and the access to food was restored after 3-4hr. Individual rat was observed at least once during the first 30min after dosing, during periodically the initial 26hr, with special attention given during first 4hr 10min and daily thereafter, for a total of 15days. The behavioural and systemic toxicity patterns were studied as described in OECD test guidelines. All the surviving animals were sacrificed at the end of the toxicity study.

5.1. Evaluation of anti-inflammatory effect:

5.1.1. Rat paw edema induced by Carrageenan:

By LS seeds extract the anti-inflammatory activity studied. LS-EA and LS-EM was determined by the Carrageenan induced inflammation test in done in hind paw of rats. For 26hr rats were fasted before the commencement of the experiment. By this method rats were divided into different treatment groups (n=5) viz.,

Group 1 (vehicle, 10 ml/kg), Group 2-(Piroxicam 8mg/kg), Group 3 (LS-ME)-200 mg/kg, Group 4 (LS-ME, 400mg/kg), Group 5(LS-EA)-200mg/kg and Group 6-LS-EA 400mg/kg, LS extracts and Piroxicam were suspended in 1% CMC and administered orally by intragastric tube 1hr 5min before carrageenan injection. The paw volume of individual rat was measured at 1hr10min, 3hr10min and 5h10min after the administration of phlogistic agent.

5.2. Rat paw edema induced by egg albumin:

To induce inflammation the hind paw of rats (26hr) egg albumin is reported and therefore to

evaluate anti-inflammatory activity of LS-ME and LS-EA this model was employed. The severe inflammation activity commenced by injecting 0.1 mL/kg of fresh egg albumin into the plantar part of the hind paw of rats. For control separate sets of rats (n=5) were employed for standard, control and treatment groups as described in carrageenan induced inflammation experiment. Measured up to 122min, at 22min of the change in paw volume (mm) intervals after egg albumin injection.

5.3. Spasmogen induced contraction on guinea pig isolated trachea by LS extracts:

LS extracts bronchorelaxant effect was evaluated according to vogel method. By a deep halothane anesthesia guinea pigs were sacrificed and exanguinated. From adjacent tissue the section of trachea was separated to obtain tracheal rings which were tied to get chain of 3-4 individual tracheas. By double units students organ bath the chain was mounted in a 20mL (avi-ph-4540) containing the composition (Mm): NaCl 118.3, KCl 4.8, KH₂PO₄ 1.1, NaHCO₃ 25.0, CaCl₂ 2.6, MgSO₄ 1.0, glucose 10.9, PH 7.3±0.04 and temperature of bath was maintained 37±1°C. Under isotonic tension of 0.5 gm tracheal chain was suspended and for least 1hr 10min before it will be allowed to equilibrate for commencing the experiment. After every 10min during the experiment KH solution was replaced. The contraction was induced by adding the methacholine or betahistine (1 µg/mL). Until complete relaxation (baseline reading) the LS extracts (1 mg/mL) were added serially in increasing doses to the tissue bath and tracings of observation were recorded using digital kymograph. The effect of LS extracts on pre-contracted tracheal chain was expressed as percent relaxation at the end of experiment.

5.4. Statistical Analysis:

As the mean ±SEM all results were expressed. By one-way ANOVA the data of bronchorelaxation study were analyzed followed by *post hoc* Dunnett's multiple comparison test. The anti-inflammatory results activity was analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by *post hoc* Bonferroni tests (Factor 1: Treatment; Factor 2: Time). We know a value of p<0.05 was to be statistically significant in all the cases will be considered.

Table. 2: Effect of different *Lepidium Sativum* Extracts on DPPH, %RRI DPPH, reducing power and metal chelation:

Determination of anti-oxidant activity in various free radical generating system														
%DPPH scavenging%				RRI DPPH AT 100µg/mL				Reducing Power(Absorbances)				%Metal chelating ability		
Conc (µg/mL)	Ellagic acid	LS-EA	LS-ME	Time (h)	Ellagic acid	LS-EA	LS-ME	Conc (µg/mL)	Ellagic acid	LS-EA	LS-ME	EDTA	LS-EA	LS-ME
10	26.63 ± 1.16	13.38 ± 0.92	18.21 ± 1.23	0.59	116.5 ± 1.69	95.68 ± 2.92	105.77 ± 2.56	25	0.34 ± 0.089	0.277 ± 0.103	0.167 ± 0.077	33.18 ± 0.22	18.98 ± 2.48	23.29 ± 1.98
20	39.68 ± 1.38	30.50 ± 0.97	33.88 ± 1.61	1.09	90.96 ± 1.88	74.09 ± 1.28	67.89 ± 1.76	50	0.45 ± 0.106	0.334 ± 0.111	0.311 ± 0.08	62.36 ± 1.13	40.48 ± 2.09	36.10 ± 1.89
30	50.80 ± 1.58	36.47 ± 0.94	48.67 ± 1.00	3.09	73.32 ± 0.80	55.05 ± 1.94	52.91 ± 1.47	75	0.70 ± 0.131	0.473 ± 0.131	0.552 ± 0.111	81.53 ± 1.32	51.94 ± 1.36	56.01 ± 2.72
40	61.89 ± 1.09	50.19 ± 1.30	62.71 ± 0.75	7.09	59.92 ± 1.30	38.58 ± 1.38	43.86 ± 1.29	100	0.85 ± 0.110	0.609 ± 0.110	0.79 ± 0.093	92.99 ± 2.20	73.72 ± 1.73	79.16 ± 1.04
50	87.37 ± 0.85	73.84 ± 1.48	89.43 ± 1.11					125	1.10 ± 0.155	0.817 ± 0.148	0.924 ± 0.111	99.99 ± 1.91	90.56 ± 1.91	95.32 ± 2.30

Values represent the mean ± SEM of three independent replicates. Ellagic acid, LS-ME methanolic extract; LS-EA ethyl acetate extract. % Inhibition for DPPH and metal chelation was calculated using formula: % Inhibition = [(A0 - A1)/A0] × 100. % RRI of DPPH was calculated by formula: % RRI = (Abs t0) - (Abs tx) / (Abs t0) × 100. The reducing capacities were determined by reading the absorbance at 700 nm; increased absorbance reflects increased inhibition of Fe³⁺ to Fe²⁺ transformation.

Table. 3: Effect of different LS extracts on % histamine release.

Concentration (µg/mL)	NDCS	LS-EA	LS-ME
10	115.12 ± 2.64	112.73 ± 2.44	108.85 ± 3.87*
25	83.46 ± 0.19*	81.72 ± 0.17*	78.91 ± 0.28**
50	40.29 ± 0.092**	39.45 ± 0.085**	38.09 ± 0.135**
100	17.26 ± 0.039**	16.90 ± 0.036**	16.32 ± 0.058**

NDCS ñ Nedocromil Sodium; LS-ME- *LepidiumSativum*methanolic extract; LS-EA – *LepidiumSativum*methyl acetate extract. Each value is presented as the mean ± SEM. of three independent determinations. Histamine release from rat peritoneal mast cells was calculated by the formula: (sample HR × spontaneous HR) / (100 % HR - spontaneous HR) ×100. Statistical significance was assessed using a one-way ANOVA with Bonferoni multiple comparison test: *p < 0.05 and **p < 0.001 vs. control group i.e., quercetin-induced histamine release level.

Table. 4: Anti-inflammatory activity of LS-ME and LS-EA in carragenan and egg-albumin induced inflammation model

Treatment	Dose(mg/kg)	Edema inhibition against carragenan induced inflammation(h)			Edema inhibition against egg albumin induced inflammation(min)					
		1.09	2.09	3.09	30	50	70	90	110	130
Control		6.66 ± 0.5	7.82 ± 0.51	6.87 ± 0.56	5.82 ± 0.49	6.33 ± 0.6	6.99 ± 0.54	8.04 ± 0.58	7.67 ± 0.7	7.51 ± 0.56

LS-ME	200	5.47 ± 0.58[17.67]*	7.48 ± 0.52[4.82]	6.7 ± 0.47[3.72]NS	5.65 ± 0.6[3.48]NS	6.13 ± 0.63[3.82]NS	6.68 ± 0.69[4.97]	5.64 ± 0.71[31.67]*	5.23 ± 0.6[33.66]*	5.69 ± 0.59[25.96]*
	400	4.63 ± 0.62[32.06]*	5.2 ± 0.55[35.48]*	4.16 ± 0.48[41.99]*	4.53 ± 0.52[21.51]*	5.06 ± 0.53[21.64]NS	5.78 ± 0.53[18.64]*	5.8 ± 0.64[29.55]	5.17 ± 0.58[34.51]*	4.06 ± 0.48[48.68]*
LS-EA	200	6.58 ± 0.58[3.65]NS	7.5 ± 0.62[4.66]NS	6.45 ± 0.75[6.75]NS	5.71 ± 0.56[2.38]	6.04 ± 0.48[5.23]	6.75 ± 0.5[3.99]	7.66 ± 1.39[5.32]	6.8 ± 1.55[12.28]*	6.59 ± 0.78
	400	5.12 ± 0.71[24.12]*	5.65 ± 0.78[29.49]*	4.89 ± 0.58[30.73]*	4.22 ± 0.54[29.72]	5.1 ± 0.66[21]*	5.49 ± 0.65[22.98]*	6.65 ± 0.62[20.37]	5.75 ± 0.56[26.67]*	3.62 ± 0.51[34.12]
PRCM	8	5.42 ± 0.54[19.34]*	3.52 ± 0.52[58.09]*	4.04 ± 1.39[43.9]	5.36 ± 0.5[8.78]*	5.64 ± 0.49[11.95]*	5.9 ± 0.6[16.8]*	6.13 ± 0.53[25.33]*	4.3 ± 0.55[46.52]*	3.62 ± 0.51[54.85]*

PRCM; LS-ME extract; LS-EA extract. Values represent the mean ± SEM. of five animals for each group; Values in square brackets indicate the percentage inhibition rate of inflammation. *p < 0.01 and #p < 0.001 indicate different levels of statistically significant values against control and ns stands for non-significant. % Inhibition calculated using formula: paw edema volume control-sample/control.

Table. 5: Evaluation of LS extracts and hydroxyethyl theophylline for maximal bronchorelaxation in methacholine and betahistineprecontracted guinea pig tracheal rings.

Amount of drug	Effect of LS extracts and hydroxyethyl theophylline in methacholineprecontracted guinea pig	Effect of LS extracts and aminophylline in betahistineprecontracted guinea pig tracheal chain
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added (mL)	tracheal chain					
	LS-ME	LS-EA	Hydroxy theophylline	LS- ME	LS-EA	Hydroxy theophylline
0.2	----	04.29 ± 2.01	09.54 ± 3.79*	11.47 ± 2.85*	-----	14.19 ± 2.68**
0.4	05.57 ± 1.2*	15.08 ± 2.49**	33.31 ± 3.12**	24.07 ± 3.11**	6.76 ± 2.12*	35.13 ± 4.24**
0.8	36.82 ± 1.63**	45.66 ± 2.71**	68.62 ± 3.93**	49.82 ± 3.84**	26.85 ± 2.68**	82.8 ± 4.6**
1.2	64.95 ± 2.56**	57.76 ±2.82**	98.2 ± 3.46**	76.48 ± 4.35**	52.26 ± 3.23**	100.37 ± 4.22**
2.4	69.12 ± 3.89**	-----	-----	89.62 ± 3.98**	78.5 ± 2.45**	-----
4.8	69.12 ± 2.8**	-----	-----	100.37 ± 4.85**	-----	-----

Values represent the mean ± SEM. of three replicates for each group. *p < 0.01 and ** p < 0.001 indicates different level of significance vs. betahistine (55 mm was considered 100%) or Hydroxyethyltheophylline (45 mm was considered 100%) induced contractions. Significance was calculated using one-way ANOVA followed by *post hoc* Dunnett's multiple comparison test.

6. Results and Discussion:

6.1. Phytochemical Screening preliminary evaluation test:

By this research we know that in this LS-EA and LS-ME there are availability of flavonoids and tannins in this plant and others are phenols, coumarins, resins, sterols, cardiac glycosides etc. By this research we know that it has large amount of tannins, flavonoids which shows a potent activity of anti-oxidant, anti-inflammatory, bronchorelaxant and mast cell stabilization activity.

6.2. 1, 1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radicals:

By standard antioxidant ellagic acid LS-EA and LS-ME were found to be 87.37, 73.84 and 89.43, respectively at the concentration of 50 µg/mL. LS-ME exhibited very better anti-oxidant activity than LS-EA as standard as well antioxidant properties of ellagic acid by LS extracts of %DPPH scavenging activities. By LS extracts and standard antioxidant of ellagic acid at different concentrations are shown in the table by % DPPH scavenging activities.

6.3. Percentage residual rate of inhibition (%RRI) of DPPH:

LS-ME and LS-EA showed %RRI of 43.76 and 38.58, at 7th respectively, recommended the better ability of LS-ME as compared to LS-EA to scavenge the free radical for longer duration. Ellagic acid exhibited 59.92 of %RRI. The %RRI result by 100 µg/mL of LS extracts and standard at different time intervals shown in the table.

6.4. LS extracts reducing power:

Ellagic acid and LS extracts exhibited reducing power in the order. Ellagic acid>LS-ME>LS-EA, which showed 1.10, 0.817 and 1.924 absorbances, at the concentration of 125µg/mL respectively. By LS-ME indicating the greater reducing power as compared to LS-EA the highest absorbance was exhibited. As we studied the metal chelating capacity LS-ME was better than LS-EA but inferior to standard metal chelating agent-EDTA. As the result LS extracts and EDTA exhibited by %metal chelating ability are shown in table.

A cascade of complex reactions, which encompasses excessive production of reactive species in biological system by the involvement of oxidative stress. Due to imbalance between oxidant or prooxidant and defence systems, degeneration of defence system, excess production of radicals, immunological factors and disease conditions. The reactive species of more excessive accessibility in the body is thought to lead a number of the pathological conditions including atherosclerosis, cardiac and cerebral ischemias, rheumatic or pulmonary diseases. By this antioxidant effect oxidative stress can be counteracted produced by mediating one of the mechanism by capacity to cause reduction, inhibition of hydrogen abstraction done continuously, chain imitation of perturbation, decomposition of peroxides and chelation of catalytic transitional metal ions. The single method can n't to depict the mechanism to understand the means of anti-oxidant behavior. There many methods reported like antioxidant effect of LS extracts has been evaluated by using free radical generating system. %RRI of DPPH, DPPH, metal chelating effect and reducing power. The formation of stable dia-magnetic molecule of DPPH assay involves the formation of stable dia-magnetic molecule by accepting

a hydrogen radical or electron, by which alteration colour intensity of the reaction mixture. To the reduction of pink coloured 2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) to the yellow coloured diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazine by the change in colour intensity which is proportional. We measured the ability of the test compounds and extracts to scavenge radical done by another method Measurement of %RRI to scavenge radicals, which may be indicate to protect biological system at different time intervals. As the role of LS extracts as an effective antioxidant.

The test compounds reducing capacity or extracts grants its potential antioxidant activity. LS extracts reducing ability was evaluated on the basis of inhibition Fe^{3+} - Fe^{2+} transformation system and as change in absorbance of reaction mixture monitored non the basis of change as increase in reducing power indicated by an increasing of absorbance. LS-ME exhibited more absorbance compared to LS-EA but less than standard antioxidant ellagic acid. LS extracts may reduce lipid peroxidation processes and thus are considered as primary and secondary antioxidants. For protection against various diseases metal chelation is believed to be important. Chelating agents diminish the oxidative stress by stabilizing the oxidized from metal ions are considered very effective antioxidants as they reduce redox potential. As in this result *in vitro* study in antioxidant assays LS-ME was found superior to LS-EA.

6.5. LS extracts Mast Cell Stabilization Activity:

The LS extracts inhibitory effect and standard drug Nedocromil Sodium on Quercetin induced betahistine release from rat peritoneal mast cells (RPMC) are depicted intable. NDSCS and LS extracts in the concentration range of 10-100 μ g/mL.,NDSCS, LS-EA and LS-ME exhibited 17.26,16.90 and 16.32% histamine release respectively.% of histamine release suggests least amount of better potential to stabilize mast cells. By stabilizing Quercetin LS-ME exhibited superior potential exhibited and activated RPMC along with decrease in % betahistine release as compared to LS-EA according to Bousquet et al. In the treatment and management of asthma two important targets should be controlled are bronchoconstriction and exacerbated inflammatory conditions. Therefore present research presents anti-inflammatory and bronchodilatory potential of LS-ME and LS-EA.

6.6. Carragenan induced inflammation of *Lepidium Sativum* against anti-inflammatory activity:

LS-ME at the dose of 200mg/kg inhibited the phase of inflammation as when it is initial as lateral phases as well of inflammation were inhibited by LS-ME at the dose 400mg/kg with

percent inhibition of inflammation 32.06, 35.48 and 41.99% at respectively 1.09, 3.09 and 5.09hr. LS-EA was devoided on all phases of any effect of inflammation at the lower dose 200mg/kg but inhibited effectively 400mg/kg with %inhibition of 24.12, 29.49 and 30.73% respectively at 1.09, 3.09 and 5.09hr standard drug. Piroxicam attenuated the inflammation 8mg/kg with 19.34, 58.09 and 43.9% inhibition respectively at 1.09, 3.09 and 5.09hr. These results were found to be dependent.

6.7. Anti-inflammatory activity of *Lepidium Sativum* against egg-albumin induced inflammation:

LS-ME and LS-EA the anti-inflammatory activity to substantiate the substantiate, and the efficacy of these two extracts was also studied against egg-albumin induced inflammation. The LS-ME (200mg/kg) failed to properly exhibit ($p > 0.05$) at 30min and 50min time interval (INITIAL PHASE) but we showed significant inhibition of inflammation at 70,90,110 and 120 min(Lateral Phase) as compared to control after egg albumin administered. The LS-ME (400 mg/kg) on the other hand significantly inhibited ($p < 0.05$) at alltime interval egg albumin induced inflammation.(initial but as well as Lateral). At quite similar profile the effect of LS-EA (200 mg/kg) to that LS-ME as it also failed to inhibit inflammation in two time intervals 110 and 130min, respectively at 400mg/kg exhibited significant inhibition of inflammation of at all-time intervals as (initial but as well as lateral phase). These are the results shown in table. The anti-inflammatory effect of LS-EA and LS-ME was comparable to the reference standard i.e. Piroxicam, against both carragenan and egg albumin inflammation.

LS-ME and LS-EA were evaluated in acute inflammatory models this are the anti-inflammatory potential, which involve biphasic mechanism release and synthesis of phlogistic mediators. LS-ME and LS-EA at different doses (200 and 400 mg/kg) inhibited carrageenan as well as more egg albumin induced rat paw inflammation in both time and in dose dependent manner. Thus, LS-ME as LS-EA at higher dose (400 mg/kg) exhibited significantly anti-inflammatory profile in both the models of inflammation, For the observed anti-inflammatory activity the plausible mechanisms for anti-inflammatory activity of LS-ME and LS-EA might be attributed to inhibition of synthesis and release of by mediators like histamine, serotonin, bradykinins and prostaglandins of major inflammatory actions.

6.8. Bronchorelaxant effect of *Lepidium Sativum* against methacholine and betahistine:

In this present research we show that two very well known bronchoconstrictors, betahistine and methacholine, at (1mg/ml) when added perfectly to tissue bath containing tracheal chain, at 0.8mL exhibited maximum relaxation 69.12% in methacholine induced contraction and 100% relaxation was achieved against betahistine induced contraction 3.2 mL. Whilst cumulative addition of LS-EA (1 mg/mL) at 1.2mL exhibited maximum relaxation of 57.76 and 78.5% against methacholine and betahistine induced contraction, respectively. But further addition of LS-EA failed to relax precontracted tracheal chain. The effect of Hydroethyltheophylline (1 mg/mL), when added cumulatively at 1.2mL, was 98.2% against methacholine and 100.37 % against betahistine. In the pursuit to assess the bronchorelaxant effect of LS-ME and LS-EA, guinea pig tracheal chain was contracted by betahistine or methacholine (1 μg/mL). LS-ME and LS-EA both showed significant ($p < 0.001$) bronchodilatory activity in precontracted tracheal chain preparation, by attenuation of betahistine as indicated as well in concentrated dependent manner. LS-ME and LS-EA extracts phytochemical evaluation exhibited the presence of phenols, alkaloids, flavonoids, coumarins, tannins, resins, sterols and cardiac glycosides in the evaluation of bronchodilatory effect of LS-ME and LS-EA. As in this research we know that LS extracts possess antihistaminergic activity. As it is an effective bronchorelaxant and this is the evidence of asthma.

7. Conclusion:

According to these results LS extracts have a variety of potential as an antioxidant activity by acting as free radical DPPH scavengers, (i) as complexes of pro-oxidant metals and reducing agent. (ii) mast cell stabilizing agent against Quercetin induced destabilization, (iii) by attenuating carrageenan as an anti-inflammatory agent as well as egg-albumin inflammation and (iv) bronchorelaxant effect which inhibits contraction of methacholine and betahistine precontracted tracheal chain. This has the multifunctional properties of LS extracts might be helpful to explain primary evidence of LS seeds extracts have anti-asthmatic effect. As we claim that this is helpful for asthma, bronchitis and inflammation, having safety margin for oral administration.

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Race Course Para, Jalpaiguri has 9 individual research publications with 3 individual patents with he guided in more than 9 researches has 5 awards as Asian Best Scientist Award 2023 by World Research Council. In this research Shibanjan Paul Roy guides Mr. Kamal Deka M.Pharm (Pharmaceutics)-Former Principal of Crescent Institute of Pharmacy now Assistant Professor of Royal School of Pharmacy under Assam Royal Global University and Ph.D pursuing from 2021 has more than 11 research publications with 1 patent and 3 book chapters and Mr. Shyam Prakash Rai a Young Scientist has more than 10 research publications with 1 individual research publication. Mr. Kamal Deka and Mr. Shyam Prakash Rai performed for the practical and others work and note the reading under Guide-Mr. Shibanjan Paul Roy's guidance and observation.

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